

**AMERICAN YEARBOOK OF INTERNATIONAL
LAW**

ISSN: 2732-9925

Vol.2, n.1, 2023

Article 1

**Introduction to the Statute of the International Islamic
Court of Justice**

Mohammed Amin Al-Midani

[DOI:10.5281/zenodo.10679437](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10679437)

Follow this and additional works at:
<https://ayil.rf.gd/index.php/home>

Recommended Citation

Amin Al-Midani, M. (2023). Introduction to the Statute of the International Islamic Court of Justice. *American Yearbook of International Law*, vol. 2, n. 1, 2-30, Article 1

Available at:
<https://ayil.rf.gd/index.php/home/issue/current>

This article is brought to you for free and open access by CEIJ. It has been accepted for inclusion in American Yearbook of International Law. For more information, please contact: AYIL@usa.com

Introduction to the Statute of the International Islamic Court of Justice

[DOI:10.5281/zenodo.10679437](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10679437)

Mohammed Amin Al-Midani
President of Arab Centre for International Humanitarian Law
and Human Rights Education, Strasbourg, France, Lecture
Fellow, Strasbourg University.

Abstract: The Organization of Islamic Cooperation (OIC) created the International Islamic Court of Justice (IICJ). The Kuwaiti capital (Kuwait City) was chosen as the seat of this Court. Its statute is similar to that of the International Court of Justice (ICJ). However, some provisions of the IICJ statute are specific, such as the reference to Islamic Sharīah (Islamic Law) and the importance given to Islamic Fiqh (Islamic Jurisprudence).

Keywords: Organization of the Islamic Conference; International Islamic Court of Justice; Islamic Sharīah (Islamic Law); Islamic Fiqh (Islamic Jurisprudence).

Introduction

The majority of international organizations function with their respective courts of justice, like the International Court of Justice, the principal judicial organ of the United Nations, or the Court of Justice of the European Union, the judicial organ of the European Union. The League of Arab States has similarly sought to implement an Arab Court of Justice; however, the draft of this Court has yet to be adopted (Al-Ash'al, 1990)¹.

In addition to courts of international organizations, there are also courts of human rights created by regional conventions and protocols. The European Court of Human Rights was established by the European Convention on Human Rights; the Inter-American Court of Human Rights was established by the American Convention on Human Rights; and the African Court on Human and Peoples' Rights was established by the Protocol on the Establishment of an African Court on Human and Peoples' Rights. It is also worth mentioning that the statute of the Arab Court of Human Rights was adopted in 2014 (Amin Al-Midani, 1996, 2017, 2020)². However, this statute is not yet

¹There are 38 articles in the draft of the statute of the Arab Justice Court. In accordance with article 14 of the draft, the Court will have jurisdiction to adjudicate disputes only upon state party agreement. The Court's subject matter jurisdiction will cover bilateral or multilateral conventions that will be expressly referred to the Court. The Court will also have jurisdiction to interpret the Charter of the League of Arab States and its annexed protocols or conventions on submission of the dispute to the Court, or if so requested (article 17).

²See the non-official translation of the statute of the Arab Court of Human Rights

in force³.

The article is divided into two parts. First, the article presents a brief history of the creation of the International Islamic Court of Justice (IICJ) Second, it discusses central articles of the statute of IICJ, covering some of the main points of contention concerning, for example, the rules of the Court and the religion of the judges. The article concludes with some questions, observations, and recommendations.

A. Brief History

The third Conference of Ministers of Foreign Affairs of Islamic States of OIC adopted the Charter of the OIC in 1972; however, no judicial body was incorporated at the time. In 1981, the state of Kuwait proposed the creation of an International Islamic Court of Justice.

The General Secretary of the OIC created a committee in 1981 to draft a statute of Islamic Court. Further revisions of this statute caused the adoption of IICJ to be postponed until the fifth Islamic Summit in 1987⁴.

in *Arabic Review of International Humanitarian Law and Human Rights*, N° 1, December 2018, pp. 327-337.

³Article 33 requires ratification of the Court's statute by seven members of the League of Arab States for it to come into force. To date only Saudi Arabia has ratified it, and only Bahrain has signed the statute.

⁴See the Statute of ICIJ:

https://ww1.oic-oci.org/english/convention/1987/statute_of_the_international_islamic_court_of_justice_en.pdf

The Kings, Heads of State and Government of the Islamic States met on 13 and 14 March 2008 in Dakar (Senegal) for the 11th Ordinary Summit of the OIC. The Summit adopted a new version of the Organization's Charter.

The 13th Conference of the Ministers of Foreign Affairs of the OIC, held at Niamey, Niger in 1996, adopted the statute creating the Court and chose Kuwait City (Kuwait) to be its headquarters (Jaghloul, Shaiban, 2017). A reference mentions that eight member's states of OIC ratified the statute of the IICJ (Lombardini, 2001).

The name of this Organization was the Organization of the Islamic Conference between 1969 and 2011. The name was changed to The Organization of Islamic Cooperation on 28 June 2011.

B. Statute of the International Islamic Court of Justice.

Election and Composition

The IICJ is composed of seven judges (15 judges at the ICJ). The Conference of Ministers of Foreign Affairs of the OIC elects the judges of this court through secret ballot from among the citizens of the member states of the OIC for a four-year term, renewable once. The candidates must obtain an absolute majority of votes from all member states to be elected. No two members of the Court may be of the same nationality. Article 3

para. c, of the statute explains that if a membership of the Court has a national of more than one member state (e.g. a candidate has dual citizenship) of OIC, he should be deemed “to be a national of the one in which he exercises civil and political rights”. The judges then elect a President and Vice-President of the Court.

Article 4 of the Statute of the Court establishes standards to choose the judges: “To be eligible for membership of the Court, a candidate must be a Muslim of high moral character, and a national of one the member states of the Organization provided that he is at least forty years of age, a Shari’ah jurist of recognized competence and experienced in international law, and possess the qualification required in his own country for appointment to the highest Ifta or judicial offices”⁵.

The oath of the judge is: “In the Name of God Almighty, I swear to fear only God in the discharge of my duties, to act impartially in accordance with the provisions of Islamic Shari’ah and the principals of Islam and the abide by the provisions of this Statute and those of the Charter of the Organization of the Islamic Conference” (art. 9 of the IICJ Statute)⁶.

⁵We will use in this article the same terminologies use in the Statute of IICJ as: *Shari’ah, Ifta* etc.

⁶The oath of the judges of ICJ is: “I solemnly declare that I will perform my duties and exercise my powers as judge honourably, faithfully, impartially and conscientiously.” Article 4 (1) of the Rules of ICJ adopted on 14 April 1978 into force 1 July 1978.

First, the judges should be Muslims, deemed to have high moral character, at least forty years of age, and have competence and experience with international law. This means that non-Muslim citizens of member states are ineligible to be judges of the IICJ. However, there are eminently qualified jurists who are non-Muslim citizens from member states of OIC who would meet the standards mentioned in article. The IICJ is not solely an Islamic Court; it is international Court, it not deal with Shari'ah, it is dealing also with international legal disputes that do not exclusively interpret Islamic Law.

Judges should also act "in accordance with the provisions of Islamic Shari'ah and the principles of Islam". Yet, there is no one single interpretation of "Islamic Sharia'ah". Rather, there are many schools of interpretation within the Islamic tradition. There are four Sunnites schools of interpretation of "Islamic Shari'ah": Hanafi, Maliki, Shafi and Hanbali. Moreover, there are three Shite schools of interpretation of "Islamic Shara'ah": Zaydis, Ismailis (Seveners), and the Ihna Asharis (Twelves Imamis) (Esposito, 2003). The important question is which "Islamic Shara'ah" interpretation that the judges are supposed to follow? The judges, coming from many different countries, will each belong to their own interpretation school of "Islamic Shara'ah" they will follow.

A judge must be qualified in his/her country to be appointed to

“the highest Ifta or the judicial offices”. Ifta is a religious point of view outlined by a Mufti or Senior Scholars in Islamic Law. Once again, the article emphasizes Muslim citizens because non-Muslims cannot be appointed for the highest Ifta offices.

I should mention that one of the Subsidiary Organs of the OIC is the International Islamic Fiqh (Jurisprudence) Academy (IIFA) created in 1981, whose Headquarters are in Jeddah, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia. Many of the objectives of this organ concern Ifta. Accordingly, we have two organs of Ifta: IIFA and IICJ. It is likely that there will be some contradiction concerning the (Fatwa) about same question presented to these two organs.

Judge must be at least forty years old. Some of the reasons for this age requirement that might be:

1. The Prophet Muhammad was forty years old when he received the message of Islam;
2. The age of forty is mentioned in Qur'an (Khalidi, 2008)⁷. In contrast, the statutes of the ICJ do not set any age requirements for their judges.

I should precise that article 4 does not mention the “impartiality”. It is only mentioned in the oath, as in the Rules of the ICJ (art. 9 para. 5 of statute of ICJ).

⁷“We enjoined upon man to be kind to his parents. His mother bore him in hardship, And delivered him in hardship; His bearing and his weaning are thirty month, Until, when he is fully grown and reaches forty years, he says: ‘My Lord, inspire me to be thankful for Your Blessings, Which You bestowed on me and my parents, And that I act in virtue, pleasing to You. Grant me a virtuous progeny; I have sincerely repented before You, And I have sincerely embraced Islam”.

On question about the judges: is it possible to elect a woman as judge? I think that the answer will be no, considering that women cannot be appointed to the highest Ifta in Islamic States. Article 6 of the Statute of the IICJ concerns the resignation and dismissal of judges. If a judge of the IICJ resigns, he should present his resignation to the President of the Court. If the President chooses to resign, he must present his resignation to the Conference of Ministers of Foreign Affairs of the OIC, and the Vice-President replaces the President until the election of a replacement (art. 6, para. a). A judge of the IICJ may be dismissed only by the unanimous votes of the other members of the Court. For instance, judges may not be involved in any activities that could lead to conflicts of interest. This would qualify as a cause of dismissal. However, a judge can challenge this decision, which the Court will then consider during a “closed session”. However, the decision of the Court in these cases is final (art. 6, para. b). The final step in this process is when the Registrar of the IICJ notifies the Secretary General of OIC of the resignation or dismissal of judges. This notification makes the position vacant (art. 6, para. c).

Judges and members of the IICJ enjoy “the immunities and privileges prescribed by the 1976 Agreement on Immunities and Privileges of the Organization of Islamic Conference” (art. 10, para. a). The new addition to this Agreement is the immunities

and privileges concerning the personnel of the Court because Article 9 of the IICJ statute mentions only the members of this Court (Art 10 para a).

The Secretary General of the OIC is required to conclude an agreement with the IICJ headquarters concerning the relationships between the Court and the city of its headquarters (art. 10, para. b).

Organization

The IICJ appoints its registrar and other officers when necessary (art. 11, para. a). The President of the IICJ, the Registrar, and its personnel should reside in the headquarters of the Court in Kuwait City, Kuwait (art 11. para b).

The IICJ is permanently in session except the period of judicial vacation (art. 12, para. a). The Court settles the date and the duration of such vacations (art. 12, para. b). The President settles the dates and the durations of periodic vacations of the members of the Court (art. 12, para. c). Therefore, judges of the Court should be permanently at the disposal of the Court “unless they are on official leave or prevented from attending by illness or other serious reasons,” which is to be approved by the President (art. 12, para. d). All the members of IICJ should “sit except when it is expressly provided otherwise”. No less than five judges are required to issue a judgement (art. 13).

Functioning

The full Court should preside to issue judgments unless the Statute provides otherwise. However, the Court may form subsidiary chambers with three judges to examine cases or expedite urgent issues (art. 15, para. a, c).

The President of the Court should approve the decision of a judge who decides not to participate in the decision of the Court concerning a particular case (art. 14, para. a). If he decides that a judge should not participate in a particular case for some reason, he notifies the judge accordingly (art. 14, para. b). The full Court is required to settle potential disagreements between the President of the Court and a judge of the Court (art. 14, para. c). Article 14 of IICJ Statute is very similar to article 24 of ICJ Statute.

Article 15 of the IICJ Statute concerns the “Chambers”. In dealing with particular cases, the Court may “form one or more chambers composed of three or more judges” (art. 15, para. a). The Court determines the number of the judges attending a chamber in agreement with the states parties (art. 15, para. b). To this should be added that that the Court may compose a chamber of three judges in order to “hear and determine cases

by summary procedure” (art. 14, para. c).

There are different ways judges can participate in proceedings. First, all parties before the Court have the right to have a judge of their nationality present at the Court, who may participate in the final ruling and take part in the decision on an equal footing with other judges (art. 16, para. a). If there is no judge of the same nationality as the state party, the state party may appoint an ad hoc judge of its nationality for that particular case when put before the Court (art. 16, para. b).

The Court has the authority to consolidate parties to a case if it decides that several state parties have the same interests (art. 16, para. c).

Rules of Procedure and the Registrar

The IICJ should “lay down its own rules of procedure” (art. 19, para. a). These rules appear not to have been made yet, or at least they have not been made public. The statute includes the possibility to allow experts to provide opinions to the Court, but they do not have the right to vote on the outcome of a case (art. 19, para. b).

A registrar assists the Court during its sessions. He prepares the minutes and signs them along with the President (art. 20, para. a). The registrar must take an oath to assume his functions. The rules should also contain provisions about the Assistant of the

Registrar, the other officers of the Court and set out the administrative rules and procedures of the Court (art. 20, para. b). For these officials, it will be important to know whether the Registrar is required to be a Muslim as are the judges of the Court, and whether their oath will be similar to the oath of the judges.

The Registrar compiles the judgements of Court and legal opinions and orders to publish them in successive collections (art. 47, para. a). The Court can instruct the Registrar “to publish any other collections of orders, minutes and documents submitted to it” (art. 47, para. b).

Competences

As with all the other international judicial bodies, the IICJ has jurisdiction over two types of cases, contentious and advisory. Regarding contentious matters, only state members of OIC have the right to present themselves as parties before the IICJ (art. 21, para. a). The Conference of Ministers of Foreign Affairs of Islamic States of OIC may laid down other states non-member to present themselves to the Court, but they should:

1. Accept the competence of the court;
2. Declare “their prior commitment to abide by the decisions of the Court”. In this case, “the Court shall fix the amount which these parties are to contribute towards the expenses of the

Court” (art. 21, para. b).

The Court in conformity with its Statute:

1. May request and or receive information from international organizations it “deems relevant to cases before it” (art. 22, para a);

2. The Register of the Court shall notify these international organizations and communicate to them “copies of all the written proceedings” (art. 22, para. b). This collaboration between OIC and the others international organizations especially with their Courts is very important.

3. The Court also decides regarding interventions. First, a state member of OIC may intervene in a dispute before the Court only if it has a judicial interest in the matter (art. 23, para. a). Second, a state non-member of OIC may intervene if it “declare(s) beforehand its commitment to abide by the judgments of the Court” and, in case the parties “do not oppose such an intervention”, agrees to respect the decision rendered by the Court (art. 23, para. b).

4. If a case is about the interpretation of an international convention, the Register should notify all the states members of OIC and signatories to this convention that they have the right to intervene in the proceeding. For every state which uses this right, “the construction given by the judgement will be equally binding upon it” (art. 24).

Two articles of the IICJ Statute concern its advisory jurisdiction. Article 42 provides that the IICJ can offer an advisory opinion to any organ if the Conference of Ministers of Foreign Affairs of the OIC authorizes it. This article raises several key questions, namely:

1. To which organs does this article refer: does it refer only to an organ of the OIC, or to the organs of any international organization;
2. The organ could be a judicial organ. Could the ICJ be one of these organs? Despite these questions, we think it would be interesting that the IICJ collaborate with ICJ and others international Courts. This collaboration will illustrate the potential for a relationship between the various international Courts.

Article 43 provides further details concerning the issuance of advisory opinions:

1. The request of advisory opinion should be written and contain “an exact statement of the question upon which an opinion is required and accompanied by all documents likely to throw light upon the question” (art. 43, para a);
2. The Registrar is responsible for providing notice to all the states members of the OIC about the request for an advisory opinion. The members can furnish information about the subject of the request. The Court may receive statements from the

member states during a public sitting concerning the request (art. 43, para b);

3.The Court may request a statement from the states members of the OIC or any other international organization if it believes that such statement would be useful for rendering its advisory opinion. The Court must also be ready to hear oral statements presented by a state member or an international organization (art. 43, para. c);

4.The state member that appears before the Court does not receive the special communication mentioned in article 43, para. c, instead it can submit a written or oral statement. The Court then decides the outcome of their request (art. 43, para. c);

5.All the member states of the OIC have the possibility to comment on the written and oral statements once presented to the Court. The President will decide the time limits for the comments. The Registrar then distributes copies of the comments to members states who presented the communications (art. 43, para d).

Many details within article 43 suggest advisory opinions are important for the Court. Article 45 gives the possibility to the IICJ to be guided, in delivering its advisory opinions, by the articles of its Statute. There is more opportunity for the Court, with this article, to refer to more articles of the statute.

Jurisdiction

The jurisdiction of IICJ includes six types of cases:

- 1.Cases concerning states members of the OIC when they agree to refer to the Court;
- 2.Cases “whose referral to the Court is provided for in any treaties or conventions in force”;
- 3.Cases concerning the interpretation of a bilateral or a multilateral treaty;
- 4.Cases concerning any question of international law;
- 5.Cases about any fact which, if established, will constitute “a breach of international obligation”;
- 6.Cases about the nature or extent of the reparation “to be made for the breach of an international obligation” (art. 25).

Any state member of the OIC has the possibility to recognize as compulsory (*ipso facto*), “without special agreement, in relation to any other state accepting the same obligation” the jurisdiction of the IICJ in legal disputes about:

- 1.The interpretation of Islamic Shari’ah principles;
- 2.The construction of treaties;
- 3.The questions of international law. The above mentioned question of who will determine the nature and content of the principles of Islamic Shari’ah remains.

The declaration of these states member may be made “unconditionally or on condition of reciprocity on the part of

one or several states, or for a certain time". Every member states of OIC who makes this declaration should deposit with the Secretary General of this Organization. He should transmit copies of these declarations to the Registrar of the Court and to all states members of OIC (art. 26, para. a). In case of dispute concerning the jurisdiction of the Court, the Court decides (art. 26, para. b).

Applicable Law

Article 27, para a., states that the Islamic Shari'ah is the fundamental law of the Court⁸. The IICJ is the first international judiciary body to adopt the Shari'ah as its fundamental law. It may well be that the IICJ's usage of the Islamic Shari'ah illustrates the capacity and flexibility of Islamic Law to respond to diverse social and cultural needs in modern times. However, we think Islamic Shari'ah should be one of applicable law of the Court, not the fundamental law. When the Court begins its work, there will be cases that relate primarily to international law like territorial disputes, for example, in which case the rules of Islamic Shari'ah cannot be relied upon to resolve these disputes. In addition to Islamic law, article 27, para. b mentions international law, bilateral or multilateral conventions,

⁸ In the draft Statute of the Arab Justice Court, the Court is based, according article 29, on the principles of the Islamic Shar'ah, the Charter of the League of Arab States and the principles of international law.

international practice accepted as law, general principles of law, judgments rendered by international courts, teachings of the most highly qualified publicists of various states. No clarification is given furthermore, it is not clear whether the “states” mentioned in these paragraphs are the members of the OIC or all the states that make up the international community.

The Proceeding

There are two ways of bringing a case to the Court:

1. One member state may bring a case before the Court by written application or notification to the Registrar of the Court.
2. The Registrar may notify a case before the Court.

The notification in these two mechanisms should be with a special agreement between two or more states under their agreement.

The two state parties should provide the Court with the issues in dispute and present their positions about the case. They should present “all the supporting statements and documentary evidence and the signatures of the legal agents of the parties or their diplomatic representatives in the country seat of the Court” (art. 29, para. a).

The Registrar should communicate and notify to all other states members of the OIC, through the Secretary General, all the applications or the agreements concerning a dispute before the

Court (art. 29, para. b).

There are two parts of the procedure before the IICJ: written and oral. The written part consists of communication of memorials, counter-memorials, replies, all papers and documents to the state parties of the case before the Court. These documents should be in order and within the time fixed by the Court and through the Registrar. Each party should receive a certified copy of every document produced by one of them. The President of the Court should give permission for any document to be withdrawn. A certified copy of this document should be kept in the case file (art. 30, para. a).

The Court hears agents, counsel and advocates, witnesses, experts, in oral proceedings (art. 30, para. b). The hearing should be presided on by one of three people: The President, the Vice-President (if the President is unable to preside), or the senior judge if the prior two officers are absent (art. 36, para a). To respect transparency, the hearing should be public except:

- 1.If the Court decides otherwise;
- 2.If the parties of dispute request “that the public be not admitted” (art. 36, para. b). For each hearing there are minutes signed by the President and the Registrar of the Court (art. 36, para. c) and the minutes of each hearing should be authentic (art. 36, para. d).

If the Court communicates any notice upon persons other than

the agents, counsel, and advocates, it should have the permission of “the government of the state upon whose territory the notice has to be served” (art. 31, para. a). The same rule applies if the Court requires evidence on the spot.

Regarding the conduct of the case and the taking of evidence, the Statute requires certain procedures to be followed in any case before the Court:

1. The Court make orders for conduct of each case to “decide the form and time in which each party must conclude its arguments and make all arrangements connected with the taking of evidence” (art. 32, para. a).
2. The Court has the possibility, in the beginning of each case and before the hearing to call the agents to produce any document concerning the case or to supply any explanations about it. If there is any refusal, formal note should be taken (art. 32, para. b).
3. The Court has the possibility, at any time, to charge any individual, body, bureau, commission or other organization to carry out an inquiry or provide an expert opinion (art. 32, para. c).
4. The Court should lay down, as mentioned in the rules of procedure, all conditions concerning questions, witnesses and experts (art. 32, para. d).
5. The Court has the possibility to refuse to accept more oral or

written evidence (art. 32, para. e).

6. The Statute of the Court gives possibility to the Defendant state to submit a counter-claim to be presented by it as response to the initial claim against the Claimant State in the first memorial. To accept the counter-claim, the Court should accept that the subject of these counter-claims is related to the initial claim and coming within the jurisprudence of the Court (art. 32, para. f).

7. The Statute of the Court allows the Claimant State to withdraw its claim at any stage of the procedures, but before the sitting of the judgement. The Court then determines such withdrawal (art. 32, para. g).

The Court can proceed as long as one party appears, even if the other parties to the case do not appear before it. The Court should satisfy itself first of its jurisdiction, be sure the claim is well founded in fact, and law (art. 35).

The judgments

When all the presentations by the agents, counsel and advocates are completed, the President of the Court should declare the hearing closed (art. 37, para. a). The Court should then withdraw to consider the judgement and the deliberations. This step should take place in private and remain secret (art. 37, para. b).

The majority of the judges present should decide all the

questions. The President has a casting vote (art. 37, para. c). Each judgement must include the reasons on which the judgement is based. The names of the judges who have taken part in the decision should also be mentioned (art. 37, para. d). The judge or judges who disagree with the judgement of the Court have the right to register separate opinions (art. 37, para. e). The President and the Registrar should sign the judgement, which should be read in open Court (art. 37, para. f).

The decisions of the Court have binding force only between the parties and concerning the case presented to it (art. 38). This article 38 of the Statute of IICJ is very similar of the article 59 of ICJ.

The statute of the Court specifies that the judgement is:

1. Final;
2. Cannot be challenged (art. 39, para. a). However, The Court should honor any request of the state party if there is any dispute concerning the meaning or the scope of the judgement (art. 39, para. b).

The Court should refer to the Conference of Foreign Ministers of OIC in case of refusal by any party to execute the judgement of the Court (art. 39, para. c). The role of the Islamic Conference of Ministers of Foreign Affairs in this situation is similar to the role of the Security Council of the United Nations as mentioned in the article 94, para. b, 2 of the UN Charter.

A request of revision of a judgement is acceptable, in case of discovery of some facts, previously unknown to the Court and to the parties claiming revision not due to negligence, with such nature to be a decisive factor in the judgment (art. 40, para. a). The Court should open the proceeding of the revision by judgement. This judgement should show the existence of the new fact “recognizing that it has such a character as to lay the case open to revision and declaring the application admissible on this ground” (art. 40, para. b). Before admitting proceeding in revision, the Court has the possibility to require “previous compliance with the terms of the judgement” (art. 40, para. c). The request should be made, at latest, within six months concerning the discovery of the new fact (art. 40, para. d). There is no possibility to present an application for revision after ten years from the date of the judgement (art. 40, para. e).

Arbitration, conciliation, and mediation

Article 46 of the Statute gives the IICJ the possibility to create a committee of “eminent personalities” or “senior officials” to undertake arbitration, conciliation and mediation about differences arising between two or more of the states members of OIC if they request it, or if the Islamic Summit or Islamic Conference of Foreign Ministers requests it by consensus. It is likely to be an important aspect of the IICJ’s work to undertake

arbitration, conciliation and mediation. The Statute of ICJ does not mention such mission.

Languages

The IICJ's decisions are rendered first in Arabic as the first official language of the Court "as the language of Holy Qur'an" (art. 26, para. a). The other official languages of the Court are English and French. The IICJ may authorize usage of other languages if the party requesting the additional language supports the costs of its translation and interpretation (art. 26, para. b). All IICJ decisions are to be issued in the three official languages. The Arabic language should prevail if there are differences about interpretation or application of the decisions of the Court (art. 50).

Financial dispositions

The costs before the Court are under the responsibility of each state party, "unless otherwise decided by the Court" (art. 41).

Final dispositions

The ratification of two-third of the majority of the members states of the OIC (57 states in 2023) is necessary for the statute of the IICJ to come into force (art. 49). Regarding amendments

of the Statute of the Court, article 48, para. a, refers to article 11 of the Charter of the OIC concerning the amendments of the Statute of IICJ, but this reference concern the former Charter of the OIC. The article of amendments is 36 in the new Charter adopted in 2007⁹. The Court has the power to propose amendments if it is necessary by written communications send to the Secretary General of OIC in accordance with paragraph (a) of article 48. The Secretary General of the OIC submits to the Court proposals regarding the amendments of its Statute (art. 48, para. a).

Conclusions

The Statute of the IICJ was adopted in 1996, 27 years after the creation of OIC in 1969 because it was at that time deemed unnecessary to create a Court. However, the IICJ has not started its work yet, despite having a statute and headquarters.

The Statute of the IICJ was prepared by experts and representatives of many members' countries of the OIC. It was desirable for this Statute to be prepared exclusively by legal experts, to preserve its legal character without interference from political aspects still defended by these representatives (Fikri El-

⁹ Article 36: "Amendments to the present Charter shall take place according to the following procedure:

a. Any member state may propose amendments to the present Charter to the Council of Foreign Ministers;

b. When approved by two-third majority of the Council of Foreign Ministers and ratified by a two-third majority of the member states, it shall come into force".

Khani, 2009).

There are many similarities between the articles of IICJ and the articles of ICJ.

There remains the question as to why Islamic Shari'ah is the Fundamental Law of the IICJ. The Court does not deal solely with issues pertaining to Islamic law and regulations but also, and perhaps more commonly, provides rulings concerning international affairs where Islamic Law is not suitable.

If we compare this article 27 of IICJ with article 38 of the Statute of ICJ, we can find common points as the international conventions, the general principles of law.

Very important to mention that the statute of IICJ adds judgments rendered by international courts. It is very good initiative and we do not find it with the Art. 38 of the Statute of ICJ initiative.

Although it is clear that, the judges of the Court should be Muslims, what about the Registrar and other officers. They should be Muslims as well.

It should be mentioned that there are some differences concerning the translation about the statute of the IICJ in English and in French! Some phrases are not clear if we refer to Arabic language.

We hope, as soon as possible, that two-third of the majority of the members states of the OIC ratified the Statute of IICJ to be

in force. It is important that OIC have a judicial organ as the other international organizations.

References

I. Articles/Books:

Al-Ash'al, A. (1990). *The International Islamic Court of Justice*, Dar El Maaref, Cairo, (in Arabic).

Amin Al-Midani, M. (1996). La Cour Islamique Internationale de Justice: Un organe judiciaire musulman, *Revue des Sciences Juridiques*, publiée par l'Institut des Sciences Juridiques et Administratives, Université d'Annaba, Algérie, n° 8, juin.

Amin Al-Midani, M. (2017). Le statut des juges de la Cour Arabe des droits de l'Homme. In *La Cour arabe des droits de l'Homme. Défis et perspectives*, Marie Ghantous (dir.), L.G.D.J., Edition Juridique SADER, édition Alpha, Beyrouth.

Amin Al-Midani, M. (2020). *Introduction à l'Islam et les droits de l'homme*, 2^{ème} édition, Éditions Universitaires Européennes.

Fikri El-Khani, A. (2009). *International Courts*, Dar An-Nafaes, Beirut, (in Arabic).

Esposito, J.L. (Editor in Chief). (2003). *The Oxford Dictionary of Islam*. Oxford University Press, Oxford.

Jaghloul, Z., Shaiban, F. (2017). The International Islamic Court of Justice (study of its status compared with that of the International Court of Justice)", *Maârf. Academic Review*, University Akli Mohand Oulhadj (UAMOB) Bouira, Algeria, n° 23, (in Arabic).

Lombardini, M. (2001). The International Islamic Court of

Justice: Towards an International Islamic Legal System?. *Leiden Journal of International Law*, 14, 665-680.

II. Documents:

The Qur'an, a new translation by Tarif Khalidi, Viking, New York, 2008.

The statute of the International Islamic Court of Justice. Resolution 13/5-P(IS):

[https://ww1.oic-oci.org/english/conf/is/5/5th-is-sum\(political\).htm#14](https://ww1.oic-oci.org/english/conf/is/5/5th-is-sum(political).htm#14)

The non-official translation of the statute of the Arab Court of Human Rights, (in Arabic). *Review of International Humanitarian Law and Human Rights*, n° 1, December 2018, pp. 327-337.